

Fig1 file name	Description
Ida.txt	NHC best track data for Ida (Fig 1a)
Zeta.txt	NHC best track data for Zeta (Fig 1b)
Fig1_KLIX_20210829_1804.nc	Data for the radar REF plot for Ida (Fig 1c)
Fig1_KLIX_20201028_2105.nc	Data for the radar REF plot for Zeta (Fig 1d)

Fig2, 3, & 5 file name	Description
Fig2_3_5_data.nc	<p>KASD ASOS Wind, u*_ASOS, u*_log_law (1D-arrays denoted by Ida or Zeta) for Figure 2a, b</p> <p>VAD wind speed and reflectivity (2D-arrays: Time, VAD Heights) for Figure 3 a-d</p> <p>V10_Diff_500m_fit, V10_Diff_500_proj, V10_Diff_100m_fit, V10_Diff_74m_proj (1D-arrays denoted by case) for Figure 5a, b</p> <p>Times_Ida (datetime for Ida analysis period) Times_Zeta (datetime for Zeta analysis period) Times arrays apply for each case.</p>

Fig 4 file name	Description
Fig4_KLIX_20210829_2302.nc	KLIX radar data for the PPI plot and VAD profile (Fig 4a, b) during Ida
Fig4_KLIX_20201028_2324.nc	KLIX radar data for the PPI plot and VAD profile (Fig 4c, d) during Zeta